

CERTIFICATE OF APPRECIATION

THIS CERTIFIES THAT
TAFAKKUR MANZILI
JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Nuriddinova Madina Raim Qizi

**LINGUO-CULTURAL FEATURES OF ASSOCIATIVE WORDS IN ENGLISH AND
UZBEK LANGUAGES**

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

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